

A comprehensive kinetic and mechanistic study of different phenols-formaldehyde reactions

Vaishali P. Raut and P. S. Jassal*

Department of Chemistry, SGTB Khalsa College, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007, India

E-mail : psj.sgtb57@gmail.com

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Abstract : Kinetic study of the reaction of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol with formaldehyde has been made at 338, 343, 348 and 353 K and at pH values of 10.0, 10.4, 10.8 and 11.2 using sodium hydroxide as catalyst. Reaction follows an overall second order rate law with the formation of 4-methylol 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol. Activation energy, ΔE and entropy of activation, $\Delta S_{\text{obs}}^{\ddagger}$ values were calculated using the linear plots of $\log k$ versus $1/T$. Effect of the polarity of solvents i.e. methanol, ethanol, isopropanol and 1,4-dioxan show that rate of the reaction is highest in 1,4-dioxan. Catalysis by Lewis bases, MEA, DEA, TEA and TEAH exhibit that MEA acts as weak Lewis base and TEAH as a strong base. A comparative study of the reactivities of different phenols viz. 2,4-xyleneol, phenol, *m*-cresol and saligenin-formaldehyde reactions reveal that rate is lowest in the case of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction and highest in saligenin-formaldehyde reaction. The calculated and experimental values of second order rate constant at different temperatures and at pH value of 11.0 agree well within the experimental error.

Keywords : Saligenin, 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol, deprotonation, activated complex, mesomeric effect, entropy of activation.

Introduction

It is well known that the resinous and non-resinous products formed by the reactions of different phenols with formaldehyde, find a large number of industrial applications. The properties of these products vary with the selection of phenol and aldehyde, concentration of catalyst, temperature and on the medium of the reaction etc. Therefore, a comprehensive kinetic studies of the reactions of different phenols with formaldehyde, undoubtedly would reveal useful informations regarding the factors controlling the properties and production of phenol-aldehyde product and in elucidating the exact mechanism of these reactions. A review of literature reveals that earlier research works were mainly concerned with the detection of major components formed during the reaction and the preparation of the phenolic resins¹⁻⁶. The kinetic study of the reaction of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol with formaldehyde has been the subject of slower growth⁷⁻¹⁴. In present work a comprehensive kinetic and mechanistic study of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol with formaldehyde has been made at 338, 343, 348 and 353 K and pH values of 10.0, 10.4, 10.8 and 11.2 taking into account the functionality i.e. the number of available reactive

positions on reacting phenol. Temperature and pH ranges for kinetic studies are chosen in such a way that the reaction can be studied moderately in the laboratory. At low temperature and pH, reaction is very slow to study the progress and at high temperature and pH, polymerisation of product can occur.

Experimental

Materials :

Formaldehyde, sodium thiosulphate, potassium bromate, sodium nitrite used were A.R. grade BDH products. Ethylamine (MEA), diethylamine (DEA) and triethylamine (TEA) were from Sigma-Aldrich chemicals. Potassium iodide, A.R. was an E. Merck product, 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol and tetraethyl ammonium hydroxide (TEAH) used for kinetic study was a Fluka AG Buchs G (Switzerland) products. 1,4-Dioxan, methanol, ethanol and isopropanol were of spectroscopic grade (E. Merck). Other chemicals sodium hydroxide and 4-nitroaniline used were A.R. grade CDH (India) products. A German thermostat (model NBE) was used for rate studies. The thermostat consists of a circular type steel bath and is provided with a tubular heating element. An

electric motor was used for stirring the water. The sensitivity of the thermostat was ± 0.05 °C.

Method :

2-Tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol (50 ml) in 1 : 1, methanol-water mixture, was taken in a 250 ml round bottom flask. To this flask requisite amount of the buffer solution of 0.05 M NaHCO₃ and 0.1 M NaOH was added in different proportions to give the desired pH. In a separate flask 50 ml of standardized formaldehyde solution was taken and the flask in the same thermostat. After 5 min, when both the flasks attained the temperature of the bath, the solutions were mixed carefully and fitted with a water condenser. There was no mechanical stirring of the reaction mixture and the flask was occasionally shaken thoroughly within the bath for uniform heating. After a definite interval of time 5 ml of reaction mixture was withdrawn and placed in an ice-bath to freeze the reaction. Kinetic study in terms of the estimation of reactants i.e. 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol and formaldehyde was made at different temperatures and pHs.

Estimation of unreacted 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol : 2-Tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol was separated from the other reactants by preparatory TLC and estimated spectrophotometrically. Yellowish orange colour developed by the interaction of phenol and diazotised *p*-nitroaniline was utilised in the estimation. λ_{\max} of 550 m μ was used for the estimation¹⁵.

Preparation of diazotised *p*-nitroaniline : 0.5% Solution of *p*-nitroaniline was prepared in 2 N HCl and 5 ml of this solution was diazotised by adding 0.5 ml of 5.0% aqueous sodium nitrite solution to get required indicator. Because of the instability, every time a fresh sample of the indicator solution was prepared.

Estimation of formaldehyde : 5.0 ml of approximately 1.0% solution of formaldehyde was taken in a conical flask. This was run into 5.0 ml of standardised sodium bisulphite solution. The flask was corked and kept at room temperature for 15 min. During this time 5.0 ml of sodium bisulphite solution was titrated with standardised (N/10) iodine solution. This is equivalent to the initial concentration of formaldehyde (*a*). Sodium bisulphite left unreacted in the bisulphite-formaldehyde was estimated by titrating with N/10 iodine solution. This will give the amount of formaldehyde reacted at a given time (*y*). The difference between initial concentration of formaldehyde (*a*) and the amount of formaldehyde reacted (*y*) at a given time (*t*) gives the amount of unreacted formaldehyde left

i.e. $(a - y)^{16-19}$.

Results and discussion

The study has been summarised as given below :

(1) *Effect of temperature and pH on the 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-HCHO reaction :*

2-Tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol reacts with formaldehyde in the presence of OH⁻ to form 4-methylol derivative :

The experimental observations indicate second order rate law for the reaction. The equation for the reaction rate is :

$$dy/dt = k(na - y)(b - y) \quad (1)$$

where *a* and *b* are the initial concentrations of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol and formaldehyde, *y* is the amount of formaldehyde reacted at time *t* and *n* = 1, is the functionality of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol, *k* is an overall second order rate constant. The integration of eq. (1) gives the following expression (2),

$$k = [2.303/t(a - b)] \{(\log b/a)\{(a - y)/(b - y)\}\} \quad (2)$$

Results of kinetic studies are carried out at different temperatures and different pH values using sodium hydroxide as catalyst. A plot of $[\log b/a \cdot (a - y)/(b - y)]$ versus time (*t*) gives straight line, showing that reaction follows an overall second order rate law (Fig. 1). The overall second order rate constant values at pH 10.0, 10.4, 10.8 and 11.2 and at temperature 338 K are given in Table 1²⁰⁻²³. As the pH of the system increases, the rate

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log b/a [(a - y)/(b - y)]$ versus time for 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction at different pHs : Temp. (●) 338 K, (■) 343 K, (▲) 348 K, (◆) 353 K

Table 1. Rate constants as a function of pH, at 338 K

pH	Initial [2-Tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol] (mol dm ⁻³)	Initial [HCHO] (mol dm ⁻³)	Time (min)	[HCHO] reacted (mol dm ⁻³)	Second order rate constant, <i>k</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	Average rate constant, <i>k</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
10.0	0.3788	0.4412	120	0.0062	3.14 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.37 ± 0.23) × 10 ⁻⁴
			240	0.0094	2.39 × 10 ⁻⁴	
			360	0.0120	2.06 × 10 ⁻⁴	
			480	0.0147	1.90 × 10 ⁻⁴	
10.4	0.3560	0.4180	90	0.0101	7.77 × 10 ⁻⁴	(9.08 ± 0.32) × 10 ⁻⁴
			180	0.0247	9.76 × 10 ⁻⁴	
			270	0.0366	9.34 × 10 ⁻⁴	
			360	0.0501	9.43 × 10 ⁻⁴	
10.8	0.3560	0.4180	60	0.0409	5.14 × 10 ⁻³	(6.24 ± 0.34) × 10 ⁻³
			120	0.0927	6.95 × 10 ⁻³	
			180	0.1217	6.62 × 10 ⁻³	
			240	0.1409	6.25 × 10 ⁻³	
11.2	0.3511	0.4140	30	0.0876	2.60 × 10 ⁻²	(2.81 ± 0.21) × 10 ⁻²
			60	0.1536	2.98 × 10 ⁻²	
			80	0.1831	3.05 × 10 ⁻²	
			90	0.2077	2.66 × 10 ⁻²	

of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction also increases. It shows that rate of the reaction directly depends upon the hydroxyl ions concentration (Fig. 2). The overall second order rate constants were calculated by the linear plots of $\log k$ versus pH for the 2-

Fig. 2. Variation of second order rate constant with pH of the system : Temp. (•) 338 K, (■) 343 K, (▲) 348 K, (◆) 353 K.

tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction at pH 11.0 and temperatures 338, 343, 348 and 353 K. The calculated second order rate constant values were compared with the experimental values studied under similar

conditions of temperatures and pH. It was found that the experimental and calculated values agree well within the limits of experimental error (Table 2). The values of Arrhenius parameters along with the entropy of activation are calculated from the linear plots of $\log k$ vs $1/T$ (Table 3) (Fig. 3).

Table 2. Comparison of calculated and experimental second order rate constant values at different temperatures and pH 11.0

Sl. no.	Temp. (K)	Experimental value of rate constant, <i>k</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	Calculated value of rate constant, <i>k</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
1.	338	1.30 × 10 ⁻²	1.26 × 10 ⁻²
2.	343	1.84 × 10 ⁻²	1.85 × 10 ⁻²
3.	348	1.90 × 10 ⁻²	1.88 × 10 ⁻²
4.	353	3.80 × 10 ⁻²	3.81 × 10 ⁻²

Table 3. Activation energy (ΔE) and entropy of activation ($\Delta S_{\text{obs}}^\ddagger$) for 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction as a function of pH

pH	ΔE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta S_{\text{obs}}^\ddagger$ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
10.00	79.84	-45.19
10.40	74.40	-64.37
10.80	63.95	-99.06
11.20	48.07	-129.99

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ at different pH values : pH (◐) 10.0, (◑) 10.4, (◒) 10.8, (◓) 11.2.

(2) Effect of different Lewis bases and TEAH as catalysts :

Changing the nature of catalysts have been studied in the presence of Lewis bases i.e. ethylamine (MEA), diethylamine (DEA), triethylamine (TEA) and the base tetraethylammonium hydroxide at 343 K and pH value of 9.8 are reported in Table 4. Due to the inductive effect, MEA, DEA and TEA behave as weak Lewis bases in comparison to tetraethylammonium hydroxide (TEAH) and the rate of the 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction is highest in the latter case. Rate can be

arranged in the following order :

(3) Effect of the polarity of different media :

A study of the effect of different solvents was made on 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction at pH value of 11.2 and temperature of 348 K using methanol, ethanol, isopropanol and 1,4-dioxan as solvents in the ratio of 1 : 1 (v/v) solvent-water mixture. It can be seen from Table 5 that rate is high in the polar solvent 1,4-dioxan and it decreases as the polarity of the medium decreases.

The second order rate constants could be arranged in the following order :

(4) Comparative rate study of different phenols-formaldehyde reactions :

A comparative rate study of the overall second order rate constant values for 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol,

Table 4. Second order rate constants using different Lewis bases
 pH = 9.8; Temp. = 338 K

Sl. no.	Basic catalyst	Initial [HCHO] (mol dm ⁻³)	Time (min)	Reacted [HCHO] (mol dm ⁻³)	Second order rate constant, k (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	Average rate constant, k (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
1.	Ethylamine	0.4370	105	0.0081	4.77×10^{-4}	$(3.72 \pm 0.15) \times 10^{-4}$
			210	0.0125	3.77×10^{-4}	
			315	0.0163	3.26×10^{-4}	
			420	0.0200	3.06×10^{-4}	
2.	Diethylamine	0.4279	75	0.0169	1.51×10^{-3}	$(1.70 \pm 0.18) \times 10^{-3}$
			150	0.0292	1.40×10^{-3}	
			225	0.0477	1.60×10^{-3}	
			300	0.0819	2.30×10^{-3}	
3.	Triethylamine	0.4261	30	0.0407	1.01×10^{-2}	$(1.18 \pm 0.21) \times 10^{-2}$
			60	0.0873	1.25×10^{-2}	
			80	0.1101	1.26×10^{-2}	
			120	0.1402	1.22×10^{-2}	
4.	Tetraethyl ammonium hydroxide	0.4226	20	0.0746	3.18×10^{-2}	$(3.62 \pm 0.23) \times 10^{-2}$
			40	0.1513	4.67×10^{-2}	
			60	0.1701	3.45×10^{-2}	
			80	0.2153	3.17×10^{-2}	

Table 5. Rate constants in different media at pH 10.4; Temp. = 338 K; Solvent-water mixtures (1 : 1, v/v)

Solvent	Initial [HCHO] (mol dm ⁻³)	Time (min)	[HCHO] reacted (mol dm ⁻³)	Second order rate constant, <i>k</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)	Average rate constant, <i>k</i> (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
Methanol	0.4217	75	0.0117	1.00 × 10 ⁻⁴	(7.44 ± 0.26) × 10 ⁻⁴
		150	0.0167	7.38 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		225	0.0217	6.38 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		300	0.0267	6.01 × 10 ⁻⁴	
Ethanol	0.4209	60	0.0191	2.26 × 10 ⁻³	(2.19 ± 0.18) × 10 ⁻³
		120	0.0317	1.95 × 10 ⁻³	
		180	0.0455	1.94 × 10 ⁻³	
		240	0.0743	2.61 × 10 ⁻³	
Isopropanol	0.4174	45	0.0501	8.61 × 10 ⁻²	(1.16 ± 0.27) × 10 ⁻²
		90	0.1191	1.30 × 10 ⁻²	
		135	0.1510	1.24 × 10 ⁻²	
		180	0.1772	1.24 × 10 ⁻²	
1,4-Dioxan	0.4108	20	0.1227	3.68 × 10 ⁻²	(3.53 ± 0.11) × 10 ⁻²
		40	0.1847	3.47 × 10 ⁻²	
		60	0.2177	3.47 × 10 ⁻²	
		80	0.2232	3.49 × 10 ⁻²	

2,4-xyleneol, *m*-cresol and saligenin-formaldehyde²⁴ reactions at 338, 343, 348 and 353 K reveals that rate of reaction is lowest with 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-formaldehyde reaction due to the reason that tertiary butyl group is more electron releasing in comparison to methyl group, so the electron density at the phenol nucleus is greatly increased, that will not favour the easy removal of H⁺ from the phenol nucleus.

Due to *ortho* and *para* directing effects of methyl and 2-tertiary butyl groups, the approaching electrophile will be directed toward the *meta* position of the phenol nucleus and which is not susceptible for an electrophilic attack. The tertiary butyl group, the steric hindrance by this group will be large. The electrophile will not easily reach the reactive center and hence rate would be slow (Table 6).

Rate of different phenols-formaldehyde reactions can be arranged in the following order :

←—————
Rate in decreasing order

Mechanism : Due to inductive and mesomeric effects 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol in the presence of OH⁻ acquires a negative charge at the *p*-position and exists as

2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenolate ion and form the activated complex with the formaldehyde molecule as shown below :

This is a slow reaction and hence the rate determining step. Activated complex rearranges to give monomethylol 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenolate ion and reacts with a water molecule to give monomethylol 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol and OH⁻ is set free to further catalyse the reaction. In the mechanism suggested above, net entropy of activation ($\Delta S_{\text{obs}}^{\ddagger}$) is the sum of the entropy of deprotonation of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol ($\Delta S_{\text{ph}}^{\ddagger}$) and entropy required for the formation of activated complex ($\Delta S_{\text{AC}}^{\ddagger}$) given by the eq. (3) :

$$\Delta S_{\text{obs}}^{\ddagger} = \Delta S_{\text{ph}}^{\ddagger} + \Delta S_{\text{AC}}^{\ddagger} \quad (3)$$

$\Delta S_{\text{ph}}^{\ddagger}$ of 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol and formaldehyde, is invariably negative and its value becomes more and more negative as pH of the reaction increases. Acti-

Table 6. A comparative rate study of the different phenols-formaldehyde reactions at 343 K

Sl. no.	pH	Experimental second order rate constant, k 2-Tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenol-[HCHO] ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	Calculated second order rate constant, k ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)			
			2,4-Xylenol-HCHO	Phenol-HCHO	<i>m</i> -Cresol-HCHO	Saligenin-HCHO
1.	10.0	3.70×10^{-4}	3.01×10^{-5}	5.72×10^{-3}	1.14×10^{-2}	5.24×10^{-2}
2.	10.4	1.72×10^{-3}	2.41×10^{-3}	1.84×10^{-2}	3.67×10^{-2}	1.21×10^{-1}
3.	10.8	1.18×10^{-2}	9.51×10^{-3}	5.72×10^{-2}	9.03×10^{-2}	2.62×10^{-1}
4.	11.2	3.61×10^{-2}	4.20×10^{-2}	1.92×10^{-1}	2.77×10^{-1}	6.10×10^{-1}

vated complex formed is unstable and distorted and its value is assumed to remain constant. Since $\Delta S_{\text{ph}}^{\ddagger}$ for 2-tertiary butyl 6-methyl phenolate ion is becoming increasingly negative with of increase of pH and $\Delta S_{\text{AC}}^{\ddagger}$ has large positive value. The net result would be that the entropy of activation ($\Delta S_{\text{obs}}^{\ddagger}$) would decrease with increase of pH. The larger values of energy of activation (ΔE) at lower pH show that OH^- play an important role in the reaction.

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